

1. Environment

- OS: Ubuntu 18.04.4 LTS
- Processor: Intel Xeon(R) E-2276M CPU @ 2.8GHz x 12
- Matlab (R2018a), Pycharm (2018.3.2)

2. processing flow

1) RC model

Figure 1 shows the flow of extracting traces and processing of three RC models. It contains 3 stages, using Pycharm (readnp.py), Matlab (RC_Trace.m), and Booksim2 tools to support the corresponding operations.

- **readnp.py** receives the output (10 files) from the Brain2 simulator as input. Extract the connection relationship of the corresponding neuron (connection_1000x1000.txt), the fire situation of the neuron (index.txt, time.txt).
- **Booksim** configures the corresponding NoC size ($8 * 8/16 * 16$), and receives the above router file as input. Then use the BHSA algorithm to explore the design space.

2) MLP model

Figure 2 shows the flow of extracting traces and processing of four RC models. It contains 2 stages, using Matlab (MLP_Trace.m) and Booksim2 tools to support the corresponding operations.

- **MLP_Trace.m** receives the CARLsim file, and generates the corresponding routing trace file according to the mapping strategy.
- **Booksim** configures the corresponding NoC size ($8 * 8/16 * 16$), and receives the above router file as input. Then use the BHSA algorithm to explore the design space.

Figure 1. Processing flow for RC model

Figure 2. Processing flow for MLP model